

1 **Shaping Synthetic Multicellular and Complex Multimaterial Tissues via Embedded Extrusion-**
2 **Volumetric Printing of Microgels**

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50 **ABSTRACT (max 200 words)**

51 In living tissues, cells express their functions following complex signals from their surrounding
52 microenvironment. Capturing both hierarchical architectures at the micro- and macroscale, and
53 anisotropic cell patterning remains a major challenge in bioprinting, and therefore a bottleneck
54 towards creating physiologically relevant models. Addressing this limitation, we introduced a novel
55 technique, termed Embedded Extrusion-Volumetric Printing (EmVP), converging extrusion-
56 bioprinting and layer-less, ultra-fast volumetric bioprinting, allowing to spatially pattern multiple
57 inks/cell types. Light-responsive microgels were developed as permissive microenvironment for cell
58 homing and self-organization, and as bioresins (μ Resins) for light-based bioprinting. Tuning the
59 mechanical and optical properties of these gelatin-based microparticles enables their use as support
60 bath for suspended extrusion printing, in which features containing high cell densities can be easily
61 introduced. μ Resins can then be sculpted within seconds with tomographic light projections into
62 centimetre-scale, granular hydrogel-based, convoluted constructs. Interstitial microvoids within
63 microgels enhanced differentiation of multiple stem/progenitor cells (vascular, mesenchymal,
64 neural), otherwise not possible with conventional bulk hydrogels. As proof-of-concept, EmVP was
65 applied to create complex synthetic biology-inspired intercellular communication models, where
66 adipocyte differentiation is regulated by optogenetic-engineered pancreatic cells. Overall, EmVP
67 offers new avenues for producing regenerative grafts with enhanced functionality, and for developing
68 engineered living systems and (metabolic) disease models.

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70 **Keywords (max 5):** biofabrication, volumetric bioprinting, FRESH printing, synthetic biology,
71 optogenetics

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76 1. INTRODUCTION

77 Biofabrication technologies are powerful tools to shape the architecture and guide the functionality
78 of complex tissue constructs, and promise to revolutionize biomedical research and regenerative
79 medicine. Through bioprinting and bioassembly techniques, precise control over the spatial
80 organization of multiple cell types and biomaterials is possible via automated three-dimensional (3D)
81 patterning processes.^[1,2] Major challenges in bioprinting of functional constructs with native like-
82 behavior, still rely on the use of biomaterials that provide a permissive environment for cell-driven
83 self-organization and intercellular communication. While this is generally possible with hydrogels
84 with low elastic moduli, ensuring high printing resolution and shape fidelity of these materials
85 remains a key bottleneck, especially when using conventional layer-by-layer fabrication techniques.^[3]
86 Volumetric bioprinting (VBP) was recently introduced to increase the printing speed and overcome
87 the geometric constraints of conventional layer-wise bioprinting approaches, even when using
88 hydrogels with low mechanical properties.^[4,5] Briefly, inspired by computed tomography, VBP relies
89 on the projection of a series of 2D patterned optical light fields sent from different angles within a
90 volume of a photopolymer, typically a cell-laden light-responsive hydrogel, also termed bioresin.^[6-8]
91 The cumulation of the light patterns form an anisotropic 3D dose distribution that triggers the
92 polymerization of the bioresin only in the regions corresponding to the desired object.^[4] However,
93 the possibility to create high resolution features comprising multiple, independent structural elements
94 intertwined into a construct remains a major challenge, especially when using multiple materials and
95 cell types in a single printing process. Moreover, given that this technique is still in its infancy, there
96 is still a limited array of available, printable materials, the vast majority of which do not provide
97 environments in which cells can easily migrate and reorganize (or differentiate) into structures that
98 mimic the native environment of human tissues. Enabling volumetric bioprinting using microgel-
99 based materials, can offer a new versatile solution to these limitations, allowing to create complex
100 3D structures embedding features containing multiple inks, multiple cell types, in which bioprinted
101 cells can rapidly grow and home.

102 Microgel-based biomaterials, also known as granular hydrogels, are an emerging class of biomaterials
103 and a promising alternative to conventional hydrogels for 3D bioprinting applications.^[9] Granular
104 hydrogels consist in packed assemblies of hydrogel microparticles (the microgels), typically produced
105 using methods, such as mechanical fragmentation of bulk gels,^[10,11] via microfluidic systems,^[12,13]
106 lithography^[14,15] or batch emulsions.^[16,17] Microgels packing to obtain granular hydrogels can be
107 performed by centrifugation,^[18] gravity-assisted sedimentation,^[19] or vacuum-driven removal of the
108 liquid phase from a microgel suspension.^[17,19–21] Notably, while individually each microgel possesses
109 comparable properties to its bulk hydrogel counterpart, packed microgel assemblies can be designed
110 and customized to display a broad array of macro-scale behaviors, for instance by tuning the
111 properties of each individual microgel, or mixing microgels with different physico-chemical profile
112 (*e.g.*, size, shape, mechanics, degradability).^[22] Importantly, packed microgels produce micrometre-
113 sized voids of interstitial space,^[23] where cells can easily infiltrate, proliferate and spread without
114 needing to degrade the hydrogel. Obviously, this further increases the degrees of freedom achievable
115 in terms of biological performance and range of targetable biomedical applications.^[18,19,24] Of
116 particular relevance for the field of biofabrication, granular hydrogels have already made their way
117 in techniques like extrusion-based printing as well, due to their unique rheological properties.^[22] In
118 fact, while on the one hand jammed microgels can be directly used as bioinks for extrusion
119 bioprinting,^[9,25,26] microgel slurries are also an ideal support bath for gel-in-gel printing, a process
120 also known as embedded extrusion printing.^[27–29] In conventional extrusion printing, many printing
121 artefacts are caused by the deformation of extruded filaments due to gravity and surface tension-
122 driven effects.^[30] To overcome this problem, embedded extrusion printing leverages printing inside
123 of a support bath, capable of keeping the printed structure in its intended 3D geometry and preventing
124 it from collapsing, even when the extruded ink is a hydrogel with low viscosity and limited
125 mechanical properties. When the support bath during the extrusion printing process is composed of a
126 microgel slurry, the microgels around the moving nozzle locally displace, allowing the extrusion of
127 the ink, and keeping the printed filament in place.^[31] However, as for all extrusion techniques, the

128 printing time increases cubically with the scaling factor, resulting in unfavourable printing times
129 when cell-laden, centimeter-scale constructs are required.^[4]

130

131 In this work, we demonstrate for the first time the convergence of VBP with embedded extrusion
132 bioprinting, hereby termed Embedded Extrusion Volumetric Printing (EmVP), to rapidly produce
133 multi-material, centimeter-scale microgel based-constructs, in which multiple cell types can be
134 patterned at high cellular densities, typical of many native dense and soft tissues (*i.e.*, pancreas, liver,
135 etc.). With this approach, a key challenge of classical volumetric printing, that is the inherent
136 difficulty in producing structures containing multi-ink and multi-cell features can be overcome. The
137 workflow for EmVP described in this work, and the different steps to characterize the process and
138 the materials utilized is summarized in **Figure 1**. As platform material for EmVP, we developed and
139 characterized a photo-crosslinkable micro-resin (μ Resin) composed by jammed gelatin methacryloyl
140 (gelMA) microgels (**Figure 1A**). These can be annealed in a spatial-selective fashion via volumetric
141 bioprinting, to produce well-defined, microporous objects (**Figure 1B**), and the potential of the
142 interstitial spaces between volumetrically annealed, printed microgels to support the culture of
143 multiple cell types was investigated (**Figure 1C**). Notably, prior to the tomographic printing step, the
144 μ Resin can be utilized as cell-laden support medium for embedded printing, leveraging on its
145 particulate composition and its shear-thinning behavior, to pattern any cell type or material in
146 precisely selected patterns within the bioresin volume (**Figure 1D**). This approach is particularly
147 important both to recreate high cell density areas within volumetrically bioprinted constructs (**Figure**
148 **1E**), and also to minimize the number of cells needed during the subsequent volumetric print.
149 Moreover, we also showed the possibility for including mechanically strong inks to provide further
150 structural stability to the final constructs. Finally, as proof-of-concept of application, we introduced
151 a new tissue engineering approach, in which we use synthetic biology tools and optogenetics to guide
152 the communication between different bioprinted cell types (**Figure 1F**). Here, EmVP is employed to
153 produce a spatially defined, co-culture system, in which a precisely patterned pancreatic β -like cell

154 line, engineered to release insulin upon blue light exposure, interacts with a stromal tissue composed
155 of (pre-)adipocytes, in the perspective of developing an *in vitro* synthetic model that can have future
156 applications *e.g.*, in studying metabolic dysregulation in obesity and diabetes.

157

158 2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

159 2.1 μ Resins for volumetric bioprinting with tunable optical and mechanical properties

160 To generate a microgel-based bioresin, we first focused on the technology to produce light-sensitive
161 particles. Although microgel slurries produced from virtually any light-responsive hydrogel could be
162 used for EmVP, gelMA was selected as proof-of-concept material for this study, due to its wide-
163 spread use in bioprinting,^[32] due to its biocompatibility and tunability for a large range of applications
164 in both extrusion-based and light-based bioprinting.^[4,33,34] In this work, microgels were produced by
165 mechanically breaking a thermally gelled, non-photoexposed, gelMA bulk hydrogel into microscale
166 particles using a simple rotational blender, allowing to turn bulk hydrogels into microparticles within
167 seconds or few minutes.^[11,22] Particles obtained in this way show an irregular, polygonal-like
168 morphology (**Supplementary Figure S1**). Obtaining a high amount of microgel in a fast way is
169 crucial when the granular hydrogel is meant to be used as a bioresin in a volumetric printing process
170 to generate cm³-scale objects. We first assessed the effect of four different milling times (45s, 60s,
171 90s, and 120s) on microparticle size, geometry, and on the rheological profile of the microparticle
172 slurries (**Figure 2A**). Results showed that blending time significantly affects the particle size after
173 45s, and the smallest dimension ($159 \pm 75 \mu\text{m}$) was achieved after 90s. Irrespective of the blending
174 time, all the μ Resin formulations showed a marked shear thinning behavior (**Figure 2B**), compatible
175 with what is commonly reported for granular hydrogels,^[22] and a key parameter for ideal materials
176 intended not only as bioinks for extrusion printing,^[35] but also as support baths for embedded
177 bioprinting.^[11] Next, the obtained slurries can be converted into a cohesive scaffold by
178 photocrosslinking, resulting in the formation of both intra- and inter-particle covalent bonds, to create
179 microporous annealed gels.^[36] The photo-crosslinking was achieved by supplementing the μ Resin

180 with 0.1% w/v Lithium phenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphinate (LAP), a photo-initiator
181 commonly used for biofabrication purposes due to its optimal water solubility and high
182 cytocompatibility.^[37,38] The mechanical properties of the photo-annealed constructs were then
183 assessed while maintaining the gels at the same temperature (5°C) used during the microgel
184 fabrication phase. Unconfined compression tests revealed a statistically significant correlation
185 between the milling time and the compressive moduli, showing how a significant drop of the
186 mechanical properties follows a reduction of the microgels dimension (from 14.3 ± 2.2 to 5.6 ± 0.9 ,
187 for the samples 45s and 120s, respectively; $p \leq 0.05$), which was always consistently lower than the
188 values found for bulk hydrogels (46.3 ± 5.7). This decrease is consistent with the smaller size
189 distribution, found for microgels produced upon longer blending time. High size polydispersity could
190 in fact allow tighter packing, as smaller particles fill the interparticle voids between larger microgels,
191 therefore, resulting in overall stiffer structures.^[39] The stiffness of the gels is an important
192 characteristic as it influences the overall mechanical properties, as well as the behavior and
193 morphology of the encapsulated cells.^[40] Notably, the mechanical performance of the annealed
194 microgels can also be tuned adjusting the temperature at which the thermal gels are processed prior
195 to photoexposure. Consistent with the literature, our results showed how photocrosslinking after the
196 exposure to higher temperatures (specifically, 21°C, **Figure 2C**), led to softer gels (modulus values
197 from 8.7 ± 0.8 to 3.2 ± 0.3 , for the samples 45s and 120s, respectively; $p \leq 0.0001$), compared to
198 those obtained at lower temperatures, known to increase the amount of triple helices in the gelatin
199 backbone.^[22,41–43] Therefore, control over the pre-annealing temperature offers an additional strategy
200 to expand the range of tissue culture applications for the μ Resin materials, closer to the requirements
201 needed for mimicking soft tissues (e.g., for pancreas or liver). In addition, smaller particle size is also
202 beneficial to reduce the printing resolution.^[44] With this in mind, with a compressive modulus of $4 \pm$
203 0.3 kPa and with the smallest microgel dimensions (159 ± 75 μ m) observed in our study, we decided
204 to proceed with the formulation of the μ Resin resulting from the 90s milling. Even though the 120s
205 milling formulation showed even lower mechanical properties (compressive modulus: 3.2 ± 0.3 kPa),

206 this specific condition resulted in uncontrolled dissolution of gelated GelMA during blending, ending
207 up with way less volume of granular hydrogel compared to the starting bulk volume. This could be
208 attributed to the local temperature increment during the mechanical fragmentation, with the
209 consequent heating and dissolution of the physically-gelated polymer.

210 To visualize and characterise the microstructure of the annealed gels, light-sheet microscopy was
211 used to image interstitial pores. Cross-sections of the volumetric stacks (**Figure 2D**) revealed
212 interconnected pores within the gels, with an overall porosity that did not significantly differ between
213 gels annealed at 5°C and 21°C (showing 23 ± 2 % and 25 ± 3 % of pore fraction respectively). As the
214 porosity is primarily dependent on inter-particle packing and packing density, this could be
215 potentially modulated blending in the slurry particles produced with a different method, having
216 different size, as previously demonstrated in other works on microgels.^[20,22] The interconnected
217 nature of the pore network, beneficial for nutrient diffusion and catabolite exchange during tissue
218 culture, can also be qualitatively visualized by leaving a drop of stained solution onto the μ Resin
219 based gel, which is rapidly percolated by dye, as opposed to what observed in bulk hydrogels.

220
221 Next, we investigated the potential of the selected microgel formulation, in terms of gelation kinetics,
222 optical properties, and printing resolution. Showing a fast kinetic crosslinking and comparable to
223 recently reported studies,^[5,45,46] the μ Resin reached a storage modulus G' plateau of $1,15 \pm 0,072$ kPa
224 in 30 s after light exposure (**Figure 2E**). Despite of the promising fast gelation, however, the
225 particulate nature of the μ Resin, in which microgels and void spaces alternate, is a primary cause of
226 light scattering. As already observed,^[5] scattered photons will distort the tomographic projections,
227 altering the light dose distribution also in areas of the volume outside of the component that will be
228 printed, therefore, resulting in printing artefacts. To address this limitation when printing with high
229 scattering resins, our group previously demonstrated rescuing of high printing resolution ($\sim 40\mu\text{m}$)
230 via iodixanol-mediated optical tuning, a biocompatible compound to match the refracting index of

231 highly scattering intracellular structures.^[5] Alternatively, scattering effects can be compensated also
232 via computational corrections of the tomographic light patterns delivered in the printing vial.^[37]
233 Here, we show how the optical properties of the μ Resins and, therefore, the scattering nature of the
234 microgels, could be inherently modulated by tuning the temperature selected for the microgel slurries
235 prior to the photocrosslinking-mediated annealing (**Figure 2F**). A custom-made optical setup was
236 designed to evaluate the effect of light scattering as a function of the temperature. A laser beam (532
237 nm) having a circular cross-section was shined through the centre of a PMMA squared cuvette
238 containing the μ Resin, and the resulting scattering pattern was projected on a photodetector placed
239 behind the cuvette. For an ideal, non-scattering media, the photodetector should register a bright spot
240 having the same size and homogeneous light intensity of the delivered laser, while a diffuse halo with
241 a decreasing light intensity towards its outer border will be registered for scattering media. The full
242 width half maximum (FWHM) of the patterns was then calculated from the center along the horizontal
243 axes with a MATLAB script on different pictures taken at different time points as the μ Resin slowly
244 warmed up to room temperature. A thermal camera was placed on top of the setup allowed to monitor
245 the temperature of the μ Resin during the measurements, and the significant drop (**Figure 2Fi**) from
246 2561.5 ± 20.5 to 2381 ± 21.2 pixels of FWHM ($p \leq 0.01$), respectively at 7°C and 18°C , clearly
247 shows how higher pre-annealing temperatures can be exploited to reduce light scattering, likely due
248 to lower triple helices content and therefore more amorphous nature of thermal gel,^[41] and permit
249 high resolution printing. To qualitatively visualize the magnitude of this effect, a drawing of logo of
250 the University Medical Center Utrecht, printed on paper, was placed behind a printing vial containing
251 the μ Resin, and pictures were taken with the μ Resin at $\sim 5^\circ\text{C}$ (temperature registered after putting the
252 vial at 4°C , which is usually performed before the volumetric printing process;^[4,5] **Figure 2Fii**) and
253 $\sim 21^\circ\text{C}$ (temperature registered immediately after mixing the μ Resin with LAP; **Figure 2Fiii**),
254 showing a dramatic improvement of the optical image for the latter, where the drawing was fully
255 visible, as opposed to the fuzzy, undistinguishable pattern seen at $\sim 5^\circ\text{C}$.

256

257 Having identified suitable conditions for microgel processing enabling the use as bioink or as support
258 bath, we demonstrated the possibility to generate high-resolution volumetric constructs composed by
259 annealed microgels via VBP. Large-scale constructs with positive and negative features (channels)
260 were successfully printed at resolutions up to $244 \pm 16 \mu\text{m}$ and $461 \pm 26 \mu\text{m}$ for positive and negative
261 features, respectively (**Figure 1B**), and an array of complex geometrical shapes and channel-laden
262 hydrogels was produced in less than 22s (**Figure 2Gi/ii/iii/iv**). Notably, microscopic observation
263 confirmed how the printed objects are composed of assembled microgels, and how these granular
264 gels are inherently microporous even after the crosslinking (**Figure 2Gv**). Thus, exploiting the
265 combination of interstitial microporosity and larger, printed hollow channels could eventually
266 facilitate nutrient accessibility throughout the volume of bioprinted constructs during tissue culture.
267 Finally, with regards to the printing resolution, previous reports on VBP demonstrated the ability of
268 the technique to resolve features as small as $40 \mu\text{m}$, when using bulk gelMA bioresins.^[5] Differently
269 from these homogenous resins, in line with the particulate nature of the microgel constructs, the
270 minimum printing resolution when using μResins is instead limited by the particle size, and on how
271 many particles are bound together by the tomographic light exposure in the proximity of small
272 features, such as the spikes of the model in Figure 1B. Therefore, although our best resolution is in
273 the range of approximately the size of two particles, in future studies further optimization of the
274 volumetric printing resolution could be performed producing smaller microgels, for instance
275 switching from gelatin blending to batch emulsion,^[47] or coalescence-based strategies,^[48] which,
276 although requiring extensive purification steps to remove emulsifiers, or being lower throughput
277 compared to our approach, showed minimum particle size in the range between 1 and $10 \mu\text{m}$, and
278 also enable improved resolution of extrusion-printed inks.

279

280 **2.2 GelMA μResins provide a permissive environment for cell encapsulation and self-**
281 **organization**

282 Having identified suitable properties for volumetric printing, the biological performance of the
283 annealed μ Resin was investigated (**Figure 3**). More specifically, the effects of the interstitial
284 microporosity were analyzed by embedding multiple cell types in the μ Resin before photo-
285 crosslinking. The granular gels proved to offer beneficial conditions to sustain the culture of multiple
286 cell types, which typically thrive only in low stiffness (<1-2 kPa) or highly porous
287 microenvironments. A common result in cell encapsulation in elastic, bulk hydrogels such as the
288 gelMA used in this work (85% DoF, 5% w/v), is that cells tend to acquire a round morphology, and
289 can remodel the hydrogel only slowly, through matrix degradation, effectively preventing direct cell-
290 cell contact and interactions.^[49] This same behavior was observed when culturing human bone
291 marrow-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (hMSCs) in bulk hydrogel controls (**Figure 3A**), over 7
292 days of culture. Conversely, in the μ Resin, hMSCs displayed an elongated morphology, with a
293 stretching area increased by more than 300%. Likewise, human umbilical vein endothelial cells
294 (HUVECs) were able to grow, elongate, and connect forming pre-angiogenic capillary networks
295 throughout the whole microgel-based constructs when co-cultured with hMSCs, showing a ~1800%
296 increment on the number of junctions between the nascent capillaries, in contrast to what was
297 observed in bulk GelMA gels (**Figure 3B**). This crucial characteristic makes granular gels promising
298 candidates for tissue engineering purposes, including vasculature development.^[50]

299
300 As additional proof-of-concept of the suitability of our μ Resin for the recapitulation of soft tissues,
301 Lund human mesencephalic neuronal cells (LUHMES) were embedded in the μ Resin to test neuronal
302 differentiation, detecting the presence of the neuronal marker β III-tubulin. Results showed how
303 LUHMES in μ Resin can form neurites that are growing omnidirectionally in large numbers (**Figure**
304 **3C**). As these cells require basal membrane proteins as attachment points, this culture was enhanced
305 with mixing into the μ Resin and the bulk gelMA low amounts of Matrigel (11.2 μ l/ml), as well as
306 fibronectin (50 μ l/ml). These comprise ECM compounds typically used in neuronal cell culture,^[51]
307 and this experiments underlines the potential to easily functionalize the microgels with different

308 matrix proteins. LUHMES were able to sprout and connect, forming neural connections throughout
309 the whole μ Resin gels 785% more efficiently than in bulk gelMA, in which the cell-cell connections
310 were observed only in the proximity of small cell clusters.

311 These results support the hypothesis that microporosity can be successfully leveraged to culture a
312 broad array of cell types. Average length of the neurites changes as a function of local cell density,
313 with protrusions measuring between $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ to $\sim 250 \mu\text{m}$ in densely populated regions of the μ Resin,
314 and neurites spanning distances as long as $\sim 700 \mu\text{m}$ when connecting more distant cells. Moreover,
315 they confirm evidence from previous studies,^[52] which employed microgels for human *in vitro*
316 models of neural tissue, leading to improved cell-cell contacts and tissue maturation.^[9,53,54] Further,
317 it should be noted that, while this work focused on a single method for producing microgels, slurries
318 obtained from particle-generation methods,^[48] could be an useful future approach to further modulate
319 inter-particle porosity, and therefore also cellular response.

320

321 **2.3 μ Resins promote MSC adipogenic commitment even in insulin-depleted differentiation** 322 **media**

323 The specific properties of each microgel impact the macro-scale behavior of granular hydrogels, as
324 well as the fate of the encapsulated cells. To further investigate how the stimuli coming from the
325 architecture of the microenvironment can affect cell behavior, we embedded hMSCs in both the
326 gelMA bulk hydrogel and the μ Resin and cultured them in adipogenic differentiation media (**Figure**
327 **4**). This choice is due to the overall compatible mechanical properties of the hydrogels, comparable
328 with the stiffness of adipose tissue,^[55,56] and for the central role of the adipose tissue in the endocrine
329 regulation of our body, which is also implicated in key metabolic disfunctions, such as diabetes,^[57,58]
330 a disease of high interest for biomedical research.

331 Interestingly, we demonstrated how the obtained microstructure is able to facilitate the adipogenic
332 differentiation of hMSCs even in absence of insulin, a key factor often used in adipogenic media. In
333 particular, a higher number of fat vesicles was observed (**Figure 4Ai/ii/iv/v**) and a significant higher

334 percentage of differentiation was observed in the granular gels (20 ± 10 differentiated adipocytes per
335 field view) compared to the bulk gels (3 ± 3 differentiated adipocytes per field view) (**Figure 4B**).
336 Moreover, Perilipin 1 staining at the surface of lipid droplets was observed within differentiated MSC
337 in μ Resin culture, whereas hardly any perilipin was detected in the bulk culture (**Figure 4Aiii/vi**).
338 Finally, differentiated hMSCs in μ Resin culture showed markedly higher secretion of adiponectin
339 (1965 ± 379.7 pg/mL), a major adipokine and hallmark of adipogenic differentiation, than in bulk
340 culture (307.3 ± 70.1 pg/mL) (**Figure 4C**). All these results further confirmed how granular hydrogels
341 address important cytocompatibility limitations of bulk encapsulation.

342

343 **2.4 μ Resins can act as support bath for multi-material extrusion bioprinting**

344 Next, as a necessary step towards enabling the generation of complex multimaterial and heterocellular
345 constructs via combining embedded and volumetric printing, we assessed the characteristics of the
346 μ Resin when applied as suspension bath. Embedded extrusion printing, or free-form three-
347 dimensional (3D) printing, is a promising technique enabling researchers to produce complex shapes
348 and overhangs, with a broad array of low-viscosity materials.^[27,59] Notably, embedded printing has
349 been used to print ink with high cell density (up to 1×10^7),^[60] and even inks composed solely of cell
350 slurries.^[61]

351 The shear-thinning behavior identified in our non-photocrosslinked microgel slurries (**Figure 1B**),
352 typical of a non-Newtonian fluid, supported the notion that the μ Resin could be used as a suspension
353 bath for embedded printing.^[11,29] It is therefore possible to include specific pockets and structures
354 made from multiple materials and cell types into the microgel constructs. To assess this, two
355 extrudable (bio)inks were designed aiming to i) tune the mechanical bulk properties of the soft,
356 annealed μ Resin, and ii) for precisely patterning high cell densities.

357 The first ink is based on a double network of gellan gum (GG) and poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate
358 (PEGDA), already proved to be a suitable blend for extrusion bioprinting, thanks to the shear thinning
359 rheological profile of GG.^[62] This material was investigated to provide mechanical reinforcement and

360 to enhance the structural stability of printed objects. The second bioink was designed to allow for the
361 delivery of high cell densities with good shape fidelity, even in absence of stably incorporated
362 hydrogel carriers. For this purpose, we produced a bioink based on methylcellulose (MC), due to its
363 ability to both modulate the viscosity of the cell suspension,^[63–65] and rapidly dissolve post printing
364 in an aqueous environment.

365 As reported in **Figure 5A**, both inks showed a decrease of the viscosity values when the shear rate
366 increase, typical shear-thinning behavior crucial for a biomaterial to be employed as an extrudable
367 bioink.^[66] In particular, independently from the strain % applied, MC-based inks showed a higher
368 loss modulus G'' compared to the storage modulus G' , indicating how the viscoelastic properties are
369 always dominant in this polymer at this specific concentration (2% w/v). In the GG/PEGDA blend,
370 the properties of GG^[67] were dominating the system making it shear thinning slightly above 10% of
371 strain, where G'' becomes greater than G' (**Figure 5B**).

372 Following the printability optimization, we managed to extrude features of 238 μm and 255 μm with
373 the MC and GG/PEGDA bioinks, respectively (**Figure 5C**), matching the diameter of the smallest
374 needle (250 μm) utilized in this study. These values are in the range of the reported resolution of
375 bioinks employed for embedded bioprinting in a granular hydrogel-based support bath.^[27] It should
376 be noted that the resolution could be further optimised by the use of different types of support
377 matrices,^[68] decreasing the dimension of the microgels and standardizing their shape, while also using
378 smaller extrusion needles.^[44,69] We, therefore, tested the combination of GG/PEGDA and the μResin ,
379 two materials with significant difference in their storage moduli (**Supplementary Figure S3**), which
380 both could be stabilized via photocrosslinking (**Figure 5Di**).

381 By patterning and crosslinking different scaffolds with increasing infill within the μResin , we can
382 tune the stiffness of the gels up to increasing the compressive modulus by 108% with a 9% v/v
383 GG/PEGDA concentration (**Figure 5Dii**). After photocrosslinking, the internal GG/PEGDA
384 framework enabled stiffening of the composite structure upon compression, to the point that facile
385 handling with common laboratory spatula was possible without damaging the structural fidelity of

386 the object. Overall, this strategy has relevant implications for the application of embedded printing to
387 create mechanically-competent scaffolds within a granular hydrogel, without compromising the
388 structural properties of the porous granular scaffold, favourable for cell culture.

389 Finally, we tested whether the extrusion process employing MC was suitable for cell printing. As
390 reported in **Figure 5Ei**, live/dead images of extruded iβ-cells at cell density of 30×10^6 cells/mL
391 showed high viability (~100% live cells post printing). By loading multiple cell inks on a multi-
392 printhead bioprinter, it was also possible to generate custom-designed heterocellular compositions, in
393 which each ink is deposited in specific regions (**Figure 5Eii/iii**). Overall, these results on MC and
394 GG/PEGDA inks suggests how embedded printing can be leveraged to produce zonal compartment
395 with defined mechanical and biological composition within granular hydrogels, therefore introducing
396 anisotropy, often necessary in mimicking the hierarchical and specialized architecture of biological
397 tissues. Notably, as the gelMA μResin was demonstrated as independently suitable for spatio-
398 selective annealing via tomographic printing, for the fabrication of highly porous scaffolds and as
399 cell-friendly supporting bath for extrusion bioprinting, the combination of these features constituted
400 the necessary premise for the EmVP process.

401

402 **2.5 Embedded Extrusion Volumetric Printing (EmVP)**

403 To enable the generation of centimetre-scale, geometrically complex constructs laden with precisely
404 patterned multiple cell types, we converged volumetric and extrusion bioprinting into a sequential
405 step process. We showed for the first time the combination of these technologies, which resulted in a
406 hybrid printing technique offering advantages of both the printing approaches, as well as the
407 favourable biological performance of granular hydrogels. According to the recent literature, EmVP
408 could be classified as *Active Null Freeform* 3D printing in the field of freeform three-dimensional
409 printing techniques.^[27] “Null” refers to how the support bath is not dissolved and discarded to retrieve
410 the extruded structure, but is kept as part of the printed model, and the “Active” subcategory defines
411 how the extruded bioink and support matrix affect each other.

412 The EmVP phases are illustrated in **Figure 6**: starting from the design of the models, the features
413 intended to be extruded and the structure to be volumetrically overprinted are saved separately as
414 STL files. Embedded printing was the first printing step: after loading a cylindrical vial with the
415 μ Resin (either cell-laden or cell-free, depending on the application), the MC bioink was extruded in
416 order to deposit cells in a pre-defined spatial configuration (**Figure 6Ai**). Subsequently, the vial was
417 placed in an in-house developed volumetric printer, where a series of light-projections, delivered at a
418 correct dose, recreated a custom geometry onto the existing part (**Figure 6Aii and iii**). Notably,
419 EmVP further enriches previous composite techniques by sculpting in tens of seconds the microgels
420 in convoluted geometries that cannot be produced by simple molding/casting methods.^[52,70] Finally,
421 the vial containing the printed constructs was heated to 37°C to melt the unpolymerized μ Resin and
422 the sample was washed with prewarmed PBS. The printing process is then followed by the culture
423 and maturation of the living construct.

424 The potential of EmVP in engineering anisotropic tissues is based on the ability to guide cells fate
425 according to the properties of the microgels, on the precise patterning of multiple cell types, also
426 minimizing the number of cells needed during a volumetric print, with a high-speed over-printing
427 achieved with VBP to potentially use these structures for high-throughput analysis. This new
428 technique addresses a main limitation of the VBP-only approach, which is hampering the broader
429 adoption of this technique: creating more heterogenous constructs, by printing multiple materials and
430 cell types in high densities. This latter condition is indeed difficult to achieve without light-scattering
431 mitigation strategies.^[5,37] In EmVP, since high-cell densities are produced only in defined,
432 concentrated regions of the vat, we experienced limited printing artefacts, as compared to printing
433 high cell densities ($>10^7$ cells/mL), homogeneously suspended throughout the bioresins. Hence, in the
434 extrusion printed extruded elements act prevalently as light-attenuating inclusions, rather than
435 scattering particles. While there is likely an upper limit on the volume that can be occupied by highly-
436 cell dense regions, future developments combining computational corrections to counter light
437 attenuation and scattering can be envisioned.

438 It is important to highlight that embedded, light-absorptive elements have already been shown to be
439 compatible with precise volumetric printing, and more extensive description of the effect of
440 inclusions and light attenuation can be found in other published works.^[6,71–73] Given the nature of the
441 tomographic reconstruction algorithm, light profiles can be correctly delivered also in presence of
442 fully opaque elements, as shown with the printing even in presence of a metal rod, as long as an
443 unobstructed 180° view of the inclusion is available.^[74] Further underlying this possibility, more
444 recently, volumetric printing in presence of polygonal occlusions with sharp angles was also
445 shown,^[73] as well as the correct printing across opaque polycaprolactone-made, melt electrowritten
446 meshes, with light attenuation peaks reported between 10% and 25% of the incoming light
447 intensity.^[72] In addition, we experimentally assessed the effect of extrusion printed inclusions at high
448 cell densities, and detected no effect on shape fidelity (**Supplementary Figure S4**).

449 Printing precision is also dependent on the accuracy of aligning the extruded parts with the projections
450 coming from the DMD. In our set up, the alignment was performed manually. Briefly, light
451 projections were delivered onto the model at a wavelength (green light, 520 nm) far from the
452 excitation spectrum of LAP to avoid premature crosslinking. This enabled the adjustment of the
453 position of the vial to match the starting angle of the tomographic reconstruction. Subsequently, the
454 volumetric printing process was initiated, using a 405nm laser line. Although effective, this method
455 is subject to the expertise of the user, and therefore further automation and standardization are
456 desirable in future iterations, to increase printing resolution and inter-user reproducibility.

457 Next, we investigated the compatibility of EmVP for the biofabrication of tissue-engineered
458 constructs with complex micro- and macro-geometry, with fast manufacturing times and high degrees
459 of freedom in terms of generating convoluted multicellular shapes. As a proof-of-concept, we first
460 printed dense structures containing a dual culture of extruded iβ-cells in a “Saturn-like” pattern
461 comprising a ring surrounding a printed spheroid, which was finally embedded in a cylindrical
462 volumetric print comprising a central vessel (**Figure 6B**). Similarly, a branched vascular-like channel
463 surrounding a central cluster was also produced by EmVP (**Figure 6C**). Moreover, as proof-of-

464 concept for the production of non-conventional, irregular geometries, a model of Einstein's head was
465 volumetrically-printed with an inner extrusion printed cluster, shaped and positioned to mimic the
466 midbrain (**Figure 6D**). For all the models, the total volumetric printing time was less than 30 seconds.
467 Additional bioprints comprising of multiple cells types and mimicking a pancreatic model, composed
468 of islet-like cellular structures embedded in a stroma with printed vessels were also produced, as
469 further proof-of-concept (**Supplementary Figure S5**). As the extrusion step is used to pattern only
470 some specific details of the constructs, the total fabrication time, including the alignment procedure
471 remains below 5 minutes. Overall, EmVP still offers advantages over conventional printing strategies
472 in terms of time when printing heterogenous cell-laden centimetre-scale objects in terms of
473 fabrication velocity, (especially when compared to conventional extrusion techniques and DLP
474 processes),^[4,75] while also allowing to combine volumetric freedom of design with patterning of high
475 cell density features in a free-form fashion.

476

477 **2.6 EmVP of multicellular synthetic biology-inspired constructs**

478 As a final proof-of-concept experiment, and to assess the functionality of both embedded- and
479 volumetrically-printed cells, we explored the potential of EmVP to create a spatially defined, co-
480 culture system in which a pancreatic cell line interacts with (pre-)adipocytes (**Figure 7**). These cell
481 types were chosen as systems to study their crosstalk are relevant for a variety of metabolic
482 conditions, including diabetes and obesity. Herein, we explored the potential of synthetic biology-
483 based strategies, more specifically using optogenetic tools, to establish engineered and controllable
484 routes of communication between the different (printed) cell types. More specifically, we used i β -
485 cells, an engineered cell line, which is rewired to store insulin (and the bioluminescent reporter
486 nanoLuc) in intracellular vesicles, and rapidly release its cargo on demand, in response to exposure
487 to visible light (absorption peak at 475 nm), mimicking what native pancreatic β cells do, in response
488 to glucose challenges.^[76] This light responsivity is enabled by the induced expression of human
489 melanopsin as photoreceptor, which triggers membrane depolarization and vesicle release upon

490 activation.^[76] As adipocyte progenitors, we used hMSCs and explored the effect of the (light-driven)
491 insulin release on their adipogenic differentiation. As shown in Figure 6B, 6C and 6D, complex multi-
492 cellular shapes can be printed with the EmVP process. For this final proof-of-concept experiment, we
493 aimed to provide first evidence that the combined extrusion and volumetric printing process is able
494 to produce constructs capable to express complex cellular functions (i.e. hormone secretion and
495 adipogenic differentiation), which are relevant for future tissue engineering applications. For this,
496 goal, a relatively simple geometry was produced, consisting of a disk shaped construct with an iβ-
497 cells ring at the middle. More precisely, hMSCs were homogenously mixed into the μResin, while
498 iβ-cells were extruded at either 15 or 50x10⁶ cells/mL, to form the circular ring.

499 Preliminary steps were taken before the experiments. First, we established that cells undergoing the
500 VBP process maintain a high viability over 7 days of culture (**Supplementary Figure S6**). Then, in
501 another functionality assay, the iβ-cells light-dependent insulin release, already thoroughly
502 characterized in previous works for cells cultured in 2D,^[76] was assessed in 3D after bioprinting. A
503 non-zonal co-culture, in which the pancreatic cells (1 million cells/mL, to match the number of iβ-
504 cells per sample to the 50x10⁶/mL extruded condition) were homogenously mixed together with the
505 hMSCs was used as control. Both insulin (Figure 7Aii) and nanoLuc activities (**Supplementary**
506 **Figure S7**) increased with the iβ-cell content (13.5 ± 0.3 and 20.5 ± 1 ng/mL respectively for 15 and
507 50 million cells/mL). The printed groups outperformed the homogenously distributed co-culture
508 control (3.7 ± 3 ng/mL), suggesting that local high density and possibly cell-cell clustering, enabled
509 by the embedded bioprinting step, are needed for optimal endocrine functionality, in line with what
510 found in previous studies on β-cell like aggregates.^[77,78] Having discerned the need to provide close
511 cell-cell contact, we proceeded to assess the effect of the iβ-cells and hMSC interactions after EmVP,
512 over a long-term culture (14 days) in adipogenic media without exogenous insulin. In both groups,
513 hMSCs differentiated adipogenically, as was shown by staining for lipids and perilipin-1. Indeed,
514 perilipin-1 staining was performed as an additional tool to assess the effective differentiation of MSCs
515 into adipocytes, as it is exclusively found on the membrane of lipid droplets^[79,80]. The higher iβ-cells

516 concentration (and therefore, higher insulin release), resulted in an increased differentiation of
517 hMSCs into adipocytes. This was qualitatively observed through Oil Red O staining for lipid droplets,
518 as well as from fluorescent staining for lipids using BODIPY, and immunofluorescent staining for
519 the extracellular matrix component laminin, one of the main components of the basal lamina of
520 adipocytes (**Figure 7B**). Moreover, the efficiency of adipogenic commitment was also quantitatively
521 measured from the BODIPY staining, which showed a significantly higher ratio of differentiated
522 adipocytes in the group co-cultured with 50×10^6 i β -cells (27 ± 13 % of the cells), compared to the
523 15×10^6 /mL group (13 ± 3 %) (**Figure 7C**). The adipocyte-specific marker adiponectin, which is
524 secreted by differentiated MSCs, was also detected in the supernatant of both groups. In contrast to
525 the improved adipogenic differentiation found in the group with higher content of i β -cells, high free-
526 soluble adiponectin was found in the 15×10^6 /mL i β -cells cultures (2206.9 ± 357 and 790.4 ± 39
527 pg/mL, for 15×10^6 /mL and 50×10^6 /mL i β -cells, respectively; **Figure 7D**). In line with this, previous
528 research has also suggested that adiponectin provides a negative feedback for lipid accumulation, and
529 other factors secreted by the i β -cells could also contribute to this result. Even though a thorough
530 investigation of the determinants of this effect goes beyond the scope of this proof-of-concept assay,
531 and of the objective of this work, which focused on developing the new EmVP biofabrication
532 technology, future experiments can allow to further tune the culture conditions, and probe the
533 mechanistic effect behind pancreatic cell/MSC/adipocyte interactions, with a degree of freedom that
534 is difficult to achieve in *in vivo* models or conventional, non-bioprinted co-cultures. Overall, this pilot
535 study confirms that the EmVPrinted cells (MSC and pancreatic-like line) both preserve their long-
536 term functionality post-printing, opening future possibilities for the generation of complex co-culture
537 model systems, of relevance for a broad array of disease models, besides metabolic dysregulations.

538

539 3. CONCLUSIONS

540 Herein, for the first time, the convergence of extrusion-based and volumetric bioprinting provides the
541 possibility to create complex structures on a cm^3 -scale in a fast and accurate manner, while also
542 introducing multi-material, multi-cellular features in a free-form fashion, a capacity that can greatly
543 expand the range of applications and versatility of volumetric bioprinting. The produced constructs
544 benefit from the mechanically soft, porous microenvironment within the μ Resin gels, suitable for
545 embedded cells to thrive. Additionally, these soft scaffolds can be easily mechanically reinforced via
546 the in-gel extrusion of structural elements at low-volume fraction. The ability to precisely deposit
547 different cell types at locally high densities and to perform zonal co-cultures, greatly enhances the
548 versatility of volumetrically printed constructs. This enables the biofabrication of composite and
549 “vascularized” structures with spatially varying mechanical and biological characteristics, which is a
550 crucial step in order to better mimic the complex heterogeneous nature of living tissues. Although
551 this study used gelMA as a platform material, the embedded volumetric printing approach can be
552 readily translated to any other photoresponsive, particulate/micro and nano-gel slurry. In future
553 studies, the mixing and even local patterning of microgels obtained from different materials can be
554 envisioned, to create composite scaffolds with unique anisotropic mechanical and degradation
555 properties, or with bioactive pockets releasing drugs or other bioactive compounds within large,
556 bioprinted objects. In addition, the novel concept of combining bioprinting with cells engineered with
557 synthetic biology and optogenetics tools to boost tissue functionality, opens additional opportunities
558 for tissue engineering, regenerative medicine, and the emerging area of engineered living materials.

559

560 **4. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

561 *Printable materials*

562 GelMA (85% DoF) was synthesized as previously reported,^[81] and dissolved as a 5% w/v solution in
563 phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Lithium phenyl(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl)phosphinate (LAP, Tokyo

564 Chemical Industry, Japan) was added at 0.1% (w/v) as a photoinitiator to induce a photocrosslinking
565 reaction.

566 Methylcellulose (M0512, Sigma-Aldrich) was dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS),
567 obtaining a 2 % (w/v) solution to be used as bioink component. A structural biomaterial ink was
568 obtained blending two stock solutions, one obtained dissolving Gellan Gum (GG, Gelzan™ CM,
569 G1910, Sigma-Aldrich) was in deionized water at 80 °C, and the other by dissolving Poly(ethylene
570 glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA, 455008, Sigma-Aldrich) in 10% PBS in deionized water. Both solutions
571 were mixed at 37 °C and LAP was added as a photo-initiator with a final concentration of 0.1 %
572 (w/v). The final GG and PEGDA concentration were 1% w/v and 10% w/v, respectively.

573 *μResin preparation*

574 The μResin was designed to be used both as support bath for embedded bioprinting and as a photo-
575 crosslinkable material for the volumetric bioprinting process. The process to produce milled GelMA
576 microgels, was adapted from a previously published protocol.^[11] Sterile, lyophilized porcine GelMA
577 was weighed and dissolved in PBS at a concentration of 5% (w/v) and subsequently gelled at 4 °C
578 overnight. A 500 ml Oster® blender mason jar, UV sterilized and also stored at 4 °C overnight, was
579 filled with cold PBS to make up a total volume of 100 ml with the solid block of gelled GelMA. The
580 GelMA was milled for different blending times (see Figure 2) at “pulse” speed and the contents of
581 the jar were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 4 mins at 4°C to separate the GelMA microparticles from
582 the PBS. After centrifugation, the supernatant was aspirated and, in case bubbles were present, the
583 milled GelMA was washed with cold PBS and centrifuged again until all bubbles were removed.
584 With the repeated centrifugation, bubble and supernatant removal steps, the GelMA particles are
585 pelleted and the same process is performed across different batches to ensure consistency in the
586 packing density. The GelMA slurry was stored at 4 °C until further use.

587 *Mechanical testing*

588 Compressive properties of the μResins gels were assessed via a uniaxial, unconfined compression
589 test, with a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA Q800, TA Instruments, The Netherlands),

590 equipped with a cylindrical flat piston. Cylindrical samples (diameter = 6 mm, height= 2 mm) were
591 prepared by casting the μ Resin slurry in a mold and crosslinked upon exposure to a 365 nm light
592 source (5 minutes). Samples (n=4) were left overnight at 37°C, and subsequently subjected to a force
593 ramp 0.5 N min⁻¹. The compression modulus was calculated as the slope of the stress/strain curve in
594 the 10–15% strain range.

595 *Rheological evaluation*

596 All rheological measurements were performed using a Discovery HR-2, TA Instrument rheometer.
597 Shear rate tests were performed on μ Resins and on both the MC and GG/PEGDA bioinks (n=3) using
598 a 40mm parallel plate geometry (0.2 mm gap). Viscosity and shear stress were recorded during a
599 shear rate ramp between 0 and 100 s⁻¹. Strain sweep was performed on both bioinks (n=3) using a
600 40mm parallel plate geometry (0.2 mm gap). The storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli were recorded
601 during a strain % ramp between 0.01 and 100%. Photorheological analysis was performed on μ Resins
602 and on the GG/PEGDA ink (n=3) using a 20mm parallel plate geometry (0.3 mm gap), by outfitting
603 the rheometer with a UV light source (Vilber Lourmat UV Lamp, Collegien, France).
604 Photopolymerization was initiated through exposure of the gels to light after 30 seconds, and light
605 was kept on for 3 minutes. The storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli were recorded during a time sweep
606 of 5 minutes.

607 *Porosity and microparticles characterization*

608 Porosity characterization was performed on annealed gels stained with Cyanine-3.5 dye (Cy3.5).
609 Samples were washed with PBS and imaged through a custom-built light sheet microscope. Porosity
610 was determined on single cross-section images and using a threshold to select the void spaces via
611 ImageJ. Microgels size analysis was performed by dispersing microgels on a glass slide and imaging
612 with an optic microscope (Olympus SZ61). For each condition, the diameter of microgels (n \geq 300)
613 was measured and analyzed using ImageJ.

614 *Scattering quantification*

615 Light scattering effect as a function of the temperature was characterized with a custom-made optical
616 setup. A laser beam (532 nm, Roithner RLDD532-50-3) having a circular cross-section was shined
617 through the centre of a PMMA squared (10 mm x 10 mm) cuvette containing the μ Resin, and the
618 resulting scattering pattern was projected on a camera photodetector (Olympus E-PL7, lens removed)
619 placed 15 cm behind the cuvette. The full width half maximum (FWHM) of the patterns was then
620 calculated from the center along the horizontal axes with a MATLAB script on different pictures
621 taken at different time points (every 20 seconds) as the μ Resin samples (n=3) slowly warmed up to
622 room temperature. A thermal camera (Testo 880) was placed on top of the setup allowed to monitor
623 the temperature of the μ Resin during the measurements

624 *Cells isolation and culture*

625 GFP-labeled human umbilical vein endothelial cells (GFP-HUVECs; cAP-001GFP,
626 Angioproteomie) were expanded in Endothelial Cell Growth Medium-2 (EGM-2, Lonza), containing
627 Endothelial Basal Medium-2 + SingleQuots (Lonza), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum
628 (FBS) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (P/S). Culture flasks were pre-coated with 0.1% Gelatin for 30
629 minutes at 37°C, followed by 3 washes with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). GFP-HUVECS were
630 used in experiments at passage 6-7.

631 Human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stromal cells (MSCs) were isolated from bone marrow
632 aspirates of consenting patients, as previously described.^[82] Briefly, human bone marrow aspirates
633 were obtained from the iliac crest of patients that were receiving spondylodesis or hip replacement
634 surgery. Isolation and distribution were performed in accordance with protocols approved by the
635 Biobank Research Ethics Committee (isolation 08-001, distribution protocol 18-739, University
636 Medical Center Utrecht). Protocols used are in line with the principles embodied in the Declaration
637 of Helsinki. MSCs were expanded in α -Modified Eagle Medium culture medium (α -MEM, Gibco™,
638 Life Technologies) supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% P/S, 1% L-ascorbic acid-2-phosphate (ASAP;
639 Sigma-Aldrich, The Netherlands) and 1 ng/ml basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF; R&D Systems)
640 and used at passage 4-5.

641 For adipogenic differentiation of the MSCs, medium consisted of α -MEM (Gibco™, Life
642 technologies) supplemented with 1% P/S, 0.4 μ g/mL dexamethasone (Sigma-Aldrich, The
643 Netherlands), 0.052 mM 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine (IBMX; Sigma-Aldrich, The Netherlands), 0.2
644 mM indomethacin (Sigma-Aldrich, The Netherlands). When indicated, adipogenic medium was
645 supplemented with 10 μ g/mL insulin (Sigma-Aldrich, The Netherlands).

646 LUHMES were expanded and differentiated as previously described.^[83] Briefly, neural differentiation
647 medium was used, which contains the antibiotic doxycycline (dox) to inhibit gene expression via the
648 tet-off system, a genetic manipulation technique that is used to spatially and temporally control gene
649 expression.^[83] Other supplements included dibutyryl-cyclic-AMP (db-cAMP) to stimulate neurite
650 outgrowth, neural differentiation and maturation^[83-85] and glial cell- and brain-derived neurotrophic
651 factors (GDNF and BDNF) to promote survival of and induce differentiation to dopaminergic
652 neurons. After 2 days of differentiation in 2D monolayer conditions, LUHMES cells were harvested
653 from culture flasks by detaching with 3 mL of 0.25% Trypsin+EDTA for 7 min at 37°C.

654 $i\beta$ -cells were obtained and cultured as previously described.^[76,86] Briefly, a 1.1E7 cell line-derived
655 cell clone deficient in glucose-sensitive insulin secretion was transduced with Proinsulin-NanoLuc-
656 derived lentiviral particles and selected in culture medium containing 5 μ g/mL blasticidin to create
657 polyclonal INSvesc cells. Next, a monoclonal cell population, was picked based on the best
658 performance for depolarization-triggered nanoLuc secretion. This cell line was co-transfected with
659 the SB100X expression vector pCMV-T7-SB100 (PhCMV-SB100X-pA) and the SB100X-specific
660 transposon pMMZ197 (ITR-PhEF1 α -melanopsin-pA-PRPBSA-ypet-P2A-PuroR-pA-ITR) to
661 generate a polyclonal population of $i\beta$ -cells that stably expressed melanopsin as well as Proinsulin-
662 NanoLuc cassettes. After selection for two weeks in medium containing 5 μ g/mL blasticidin and 1
663 μ g/mL puromycin, the monoclonal $i\beta$ -cells were sorted by means of FACS (Becton Dickinson LSRII
664 Fortessa flow cytometer) and screened for blue-light-responsive nanoLuc secretion. $i\beta$ -cell were
665 cultured in RPMI 1640 Medium, GlutaMAX™, HEPES (Gibco™, Life technologies) supplemented
666 with FBS (10% v/v) and 1% P/S and used at passage 3-4.

667 All cells were cultured in a 95% humidified incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂.

668 *Volumetric printing*

669 A custom-built volumetric printer was used for the volumetric printing step. The optical system was
670 comprised of a 405nm 1W diode laser (Ushio HL40033G) mounted on a temperature-controlled
671 mount (Thorlabs LDM90/M), and a digital micromirror device (DMD) (Vialux v7000 HiSpeed). A
672 cylindrical vial (to be used as the cylindrical print volume) of inner diameter 13.2mm was filled with
673 the μ Resin, and vertically suspended within the rotary stage. The vial was also immersed within a
674 water-filled 40mm square cuvette (Hellma 704.002-OG) containing an index-matching liquid needed
675 to minimise distortions resulting from the curvature of the vial walls. A MATLAB code was used to
676 operate the device. After printing, the thermally gelled μ Resin was gently washed with pre-warmed
677 PBS at 37° C to remove the uncrosslinked material from the printed structures.

678 *Extrusion (bio)printing*

679 Three-dimensional (bio)printing experiments were performed with a 3D Discovery bioprinter
680 (regenHu, Switzerland), using a pneumatic-driven extrusion printhead. For printing evaluation, 3 mL
681 syringes were loaded with 1 mL of Cy-3.5 stained bioink (both for GG/PEGDA and MC), three
682 different needles (18G, 23G and 25G) and three different printing speeds (2, 3, 4 and 5 mm/s) were
683 tested to characterize the filaments width. Images (n = 5) of S-shape embedded filaments were taken
684 with a confocal microscope (SPX8, Leica Microsystems, The Netherlands) and analyzed with ImageJ.
685 For mechanical reinforcement of μ Resin gels, GG/PGEDA based filaments were printed at 5 mm/s
686 speed with a 25G needle (250 μ m diameter) in different S-shape layers.

687 For cell viability after printing, i β -cells were printed at 5 mm/s speed with a 25G needle (250 μ m
688 diameter), and cell viability was evaluated using a live/dead assay (calcein AM/ethidium homodimer,
689 Thermo Fischer Scientific, The Netherlands) on gels (n = 3).

690 For multicellular extrusion printing (Figure 5Cii/iii) i β -cells were pre-stained (Vybrant™ Multicolor
691 Cell-Labeling Kit, Thermo Fischer Scientific, The Netherlands) printed at 5 mm/s speed with a 25G
692 needle (250 μ m diameter). All G-codes were manually written.

693 *Embedded Volumetric Printing (EmVP)*

694 The features meant to be extruded and the structure to be volumetrically overprint were designed and
695 saved separately as STL files. First, a cylindrical vial was loaded with the μ Resin at 4°C (either cell-
696 laden or cell-free, depending on the application) + 0.1% w/v LAP, everything was then gently mixed
697 directly in the printing vial. The vial was then placed in a 3D Discovery extrusion printer (regenHu,
698 Switzerland) and kept in place through a custom printed holder. 3 mL syringes were loaded with 1
699 mL of (bio)ink and the G-codes of the extruded features were manually written. Subsequently,
700 keeping the vial protected from light exposure to prevent the crosslinking of the μ Resin, the vial was
701 placed into a custom-built volumetric printer. To align the extruded features with the model intended
702 to be overprinted, a first series of light-projections was delivered on the rotating vial with a 520 nm
703 laser, in order to prevent the crosslinking during this calibration process. Therefore, light-projections
704 of the model meant to be volumetrically printed were delivered with a 405 nm laser, until the curing
705 of the μ Resin was achieved. Finally, the vial was heated to 37°C to melt the unpolymerized μ Resin
706 and the sample was washed with prewarmed PBS.

707 *LipidTox, Phalloidin and β III-tubulin staining*

708 Gels were submerged in 0.1% Triton-100 and incubated at room temperature for 15 mins to allow
709 permeabilization of the cell membrane. To prevent non-specific binding of antibodies to membrane
710 proteins, gels were washed 3 times x 5 minutes with a 3% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA, Sigma)
711 blocking solution in PBS. To stain β III-tubulin on LUHMES laden gels, a primary mouse antibody
712 (1:500) was used and gels were stained in the dark at 4°C overnight. After the incubation period, the
713 samples were washed at low rocker speed with PBS 2 times for 5 hrs. Next, secondary antibodies
714 diluted in the BSA solution were added to the samples and incubated in the dark at 4°C overnight,
715 using goat antimouse IgG AlexaFluor 488 (Invitrogen; 2mg/ml). Following this step, the nuclei were
716 stained at room temperature for 15 minutes with 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI)(Sigma
717 Aldrich, D9542, 1:500, 1 mg/ml) to yield a blue nucleic fluorescence by binding to nucleic acids.

718 To stain phalloidin on MSCs laden gels, phalloidin (Invitrogen, Alexa Fluor 488 Phalloidin) (1:200)
719 was used, and gels were stained in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. Nuclei were stained
720 at room temperature for 3 minutes with DAPI (Sigma Aldrich, D9542, 1:500, 1 mg/ml).

721 To stain lipid vesicles on differentiated adipocytes, LipidTox (Invitrogen, HCS LipidTOX Green
722 Neutral Lipid Stain)(1:200) was used, and gels were stained in the dark at room temperature for 3
723 hours. Nuclei were stained at room temperature for 3 minutes with DAPI (Sigma Aldrich, D9542,
724 1:500, 1 mg/ml). All samples were washed with PBS and covered with aluminium foil until imaging.

725 *Oil red O and BODIPY staining*

726 Gels were embedded in Tissue-Tek (Sakura Finetek, Torrance, CA, USA) and incubated overnight
727 in a wet chamber at room temperature. The samples were snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen the following
728 day, cut into 6 µm sections using a cryostat (CM 3050S, Leica, Wetzlar, Germany), and transferred
729 onto microscope slides. The slides were then soaked in ddH₂O for 30 s to dissolve residual Tissue-
730 Tek®. To visualize lipid content, sections were stained with Oil Red O (3 mg/mL Oil Red O in 60%
731 isopropanol; Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) for 6 minutes. After staining, the slides were
732 washed under cold running water for 10 min and then coverslips were mounted with glycergel (Dako,
733 Hamburg, Germany). As an additional lipid visualization, sections were stained with BODIPY
734 493/503 (ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA, USA) diluted 1:500 in PBS for 30 min at room temperature,
735 washed three times with PBS and mounted with DAPI mounting medium ImmunoSelect (Dako,
736 Hamburg, Germany). Images were taken with a fluorescence microscope (Olympus BX51/DP71).

737 *Perilipin 1 and Laminin staining*

738 Antigen retrieval was performed using proteinase K digestion for 10 min at room temperature,
739 followed by three washing steps with PBS + 0.2% Triton-X100. For perilipin staining, samples were
740 incubated in citric acid buffer (10X citric acid buffer pH 6.0, ab64214, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) at
741 100°C for 5 min, cooled at RT for 20 minutes and washed with PBS. Cryosections were blocked with
742 1% bovine serum albumin in PBS for 1 h at room temperature and incubated with primary antibodies
743 (anti-perilipin 1, PA5-72921, 1:200, ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA, USA; anti-laminin, ab11575,

744 1:200, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) diluted in 1% BSA in PBS. After incubation in a humidified chamber
745 overnight at room temperature, cryosections were washed three times with PBS and incubated with
746 the secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit Alexa488, 111-545-144, 1:400, Biozol, Eching, Germany;
747 diluted in 1% BSA in PBS) in a darkened humidified chamber for 1 h at room temperature. After
748 three additional washing steps in PBS, sections were mounted with DAPI mounting medium
749 ImmunoSelect (Dako, Hamburg, Germany), and images were taken with a fluorescence microscope
750 (Olympus BX51/DP71 and Zeiss Colibri7) and post-processed with Olympus CellSense Dimensions
751 Software.

752 *Adiponectin and insulin ELISA*

753 Adiponectin concentrations were determined using human adiponectin/Acrp30 DuoSet ELISA (R&D
754 Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions. The levels of mouse
755 insulin in culture supernatants were quantified with a Rat/Mouse Insulin ELISA kit (Merckodia; cat.
756 no.10-1232-01) following the manufacturer's instructions.

757 *Statistical Analyzes*

758 Results were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.). Statistical analysis was performed using
759 GraphPad Prism 8.0.2 (GraphPad Software, USA). Comparisons between multiple (> 2) experimental
760 groups were assessed via one or two-way ANOVAs, followed by post hoc Bonferroni correction to
761 test differences between groups. Student's t-test was performed between 2 experimental groups for
762 statistical analysis. Unpaired t-test was used for parametric comparisons of data sets. Non-parametric
763 tests were used when normality could not be assumed. Differences were considered significant when
764 $p < 0.05$. Significance is expressed on graphs as follows: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$,
765 **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

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779 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

780 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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783 **FIGURES**

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Volumetric bioprinting of microgel-based materials allows to rapidly create highly porous 3D structures embedding key functional features with multiple materials and cell types.

787

788 **Figure 1:** Workflow detailing the different steps towards the development and characterization of the
 789 Embedded Extrusion Volumetric Printing process, as a new biofabrication approach to enable
 790 microgel constructs and multimaterial elements in volumetric printing. A) Preparation and
 791 characterization of a μ Resin composed of gelatin-derived microparticles. Mechanical, rheological
 792 and optical properties are analyzed and optimized to ensure biological performance and transparency
 793 suitable for the tomographic printing process. B) The μ Resin were proven to be a suitable biomaterial
 794 to create granular structures via volumetric printing. Scale bars: 1 mm. C) Biological characterization
 795 of the μ Resin, which offers a soft and highly porous microenvironment to the encapsulated cells.
 796 Scale bar: 100 μm . D) The μ Resin bath was then studied for its ability to permit embedded extrusion

797 bioprinting, allowing to produce localized regions and precisely patterned structures containing high
798 cell concentration. Scale bar: 4 mm. E) These cell-dense areas become heterocellular element in more
799 complex architectures upon performing the Volumetric (bio)Printing step, to impart the final 3D
800 shape to multicellular and multimaterial constructs Scale bar = 1 mm. F) Finally, a proof-of-
801 functionality of cells subjected to the whole EmVP process was provided, utilizing extruded iβ-
802 pancreatic cells, secreting insulin upon blue light exposure, which influenced the adipogenic
803 differentiation of hMSC loaded into the μResin.

804

806 **Figure 2:** Characterisation of the photo-crosslinkable μ Resin based on jammed gelMA
807 microparticles. A) quantification of the microparticles dimension related to the milling time of the
808 thermally-gelated gelMA. B) Representative (n=3) rheological properties of the microgel slurries
809 obtained at different milling times. C) Compressive mechanical properties of the microparticle-based
810 gels (n=4) crosslinked at 5°C and 21°C. D) Porosity (n=6) characterization of (i) bulk and (ii) μ Resin
811 gels, with a cross section of the (iii) μ Resin gel showing the particulate, porous microstructure. Scale
812 bars: i,ii = 2.5 mm; iii = 200 μ m. E) Representative (n=3) crosslinking kinetics after light exposure
813 of the bioresin formulation obtained by milling for 90s. F) Characterisation of the optical properties
814 (light scattering) of the microparticle-based bioresin as a function of the temperature (n=3), and
815 micrographs paired with thermal photography of the vials containing the bioresin at (i) 5°C and (ii)
816 21°C. Scale bars: ii, iii = 6 mm. G) Volumetrically bioprinted models with additional negative
817 features (open perfusable channels). Branched vasculature (i) CAD model and (ii) light sheet scan
818 reconstructions, digitally cropped to the central region to facilitate 3D visualization of the hollow
819 features. Pancreas models with duct, (iii) CAD model and (iv) light sheet scan reconstructions. Scale
820 bars: 3 mm. Stereomicroscopy image of (v) test print model: a hollow circular structure with a thin
821 wavy central strut measuring obtained via volumetric printing of the bioresin formulation obtained
822 after milling for 90s, with a (vi) close-up image to highlight the particulate nature of the constructs,
823 and a (vii) 3D reconstruction of the particulate/porous network microstructure. Scale bars: ii, iv, v =
824 2 mm; vi = 500 μ m.

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827 **Figure 3:** Effect of the microstructure of the microgel based gels on cell behavior. A) Morphology of
 828 hMSCs at a cell density of 5M cells/mL in (i) bulk (scale bar: 400 μm) (ii) gelMA μResin (scale bar:
 829 400 μm), (iii) gelMA μResin (scale bar: 250 μm) and (iv) stretching % area quantification (day 7
 830 post-encapsulation, n = 3). B) HUVEC cells at a density of 2.5M cells/mL in (i) bulk (scale bars: 750
 831 μm) (ii) gelMA μResin (scale bar: 750 μm), (iii) gelMA μResin (scale bar: 400 μm) and (iv)
 832 quantification of the amount of nascent capillary junctions (day 7 post-encapsulation, n = 3). C)
 833 LUHMES cells at a cell density of 10M cells/mL in (i) bulk and (ii, iii) gelMA μResin (scale bars: i
 834 = 100 μm; ii,iii = 200 μm) and (iv) quantification of the amounts of neuronal junctions (day 8 post-
 835 encapsulation, n = 3).

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838 **Figure 4:** Effect of the microstructure of the hydrogels on hMSC cell differentiation into adipocytes.

839 A) Comparison between gelMA bulk (i, ii, iii) and μ Resin (iv, v, vi) constructs, showing staining for

840 the cell membrane (Vybrant DiD), fat vesicles (LipidTox) (whole mount staining) and Perilipin 1

841 immunostaining (cryosections). Nuclei are counterstained with DAPI. B) Quantification of the

842 amount of adipocytes per field of view in bulk and gelMA μ Resin constructs, cultured without insulin

843 in the differentiation medium (n=6). C) Adiponectin concentration in the supernatant of bulk and

844 gelMA μ Resin constructs (n=3). Scale bars: i, ii, iv = 100 μ m; iii, vi = 50 μ m; v = 20 μ m.

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848 **Figure 5:** Characterization of the Methylcellulose and GG/PEGDA based bioinks for embedded
 849 bioprinting. Representative curves (n=3) for the shear-dependency of ink A) viscosity, and B) storage
 850 and loss moduli. C) Printing accuracy of the two formulations, estimated measuring the filament
 851 width as a function of the nozzle diameter and printhead translational velocity. D) Support ink: (i)
 852 representative (n=3) crosslinking kinetics after light exposure of the GG/PEGDA based bioink and
 853 (ii) compressive mechanical properties of the μ Resin reinforced with GG/PEGDA scaffolds at
 854 different volume ratio. E) Cellular bioink: (i) representative live/dead image of extruded $i\beta$ -cells at a
 855 cell density of 30 million cells/mL (scale bar: 1 mm). (ii,iii) $i\beta$ -cells stained with lipophilic membrane
 856 dyes, extruded with multiple printheads at a density of 30 million cells/mL (scale bar: 750 μ m).

A)

Direct extrusion in the volumetric printer vial

Alignment of the vial within the volumetric set-up and overprinting of the final model

859 **Figure 6:** Embedded Extrusion Volumetric Printing (EmVP). A) Sequential steps of the process. (i)
860 The vial containing the μ Resin is first patterned with the desired cell type and geometry via extrusion
861 bioprinting. Subsequently, (ii) the vial loaded in the volumetric printer (ii) where the light will shape
862 the final structure intertwined with the extruded features (iii). B) Complex co-culture model
863 comprising two different $i\beta$ -cells groups (stained with different fluorescent lipophilic membrane
864 dyes), embedded in a volumetrically printed structure with a central channel. Scale bars: ii = 4 mm,
865 iii = 2 mm. C) Example of complex structure model with a branched vasculature; (i) STL design, ii)
866 stereomicrograph, and iii) light-sheet scan reconstructions, digitally cropped to the central region to
867 facilitate visualization of the channels and of the extruded feature. Scale bars: ii = 4 mm, iii = 6 mm.
868 D) Example of complex structure model consisting of the profile of Albert Einstein (with permission
869 of the Albert Einstein Archives, the Hebrew University of Jerusalem. This image cannot be reused in
870 other media or publications), with a central portion of the brain produced by extrusion printing; (i)
871 STL design, ii) stereomicrograph, and iii) light-sheet scan reconstructions. Scale bars: 4 mm.
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875 **Figure 7:** EmVP of multicellular synthetic biology-inspired constructs. A) Schematic representation
 876 of the experimental set-up, consisting of extruded rings of $i\beta$ -cells at different concentrations
 877 embedded in the volumetrically bioprinted gelMA μ Resin, which is laden with hMSCs. (i)
 878 Quantification of the secreted insulin in the supernatant of co-cultured constructs (n=3) over 2 days
 879 culture period (timespan between two consecutive culture media refreshments) (cc = 50x10⁶ $i\beta$ -cells
 880 /mL not extruded). B) Histological staining for fat vesicles using Oil Red O and BODIPY, and

881 immunofluorescent staining for perilipin 1, and laminin, in samples carrying the two EmVP iβ-cells
882 concentrations. Scale bars in B) are: left column = 50 μm, right column = 20 μm. Quantification of
883 the C) amount of differentiated adipocytes (n=6), and of D) adiponectin secreted in the supernatant
884 of samples with the two EmVP iβ-cells concentrations (n=3).

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1037 **Supporting information**

1038 **Shaping Synthetic Multicellular and Anisotropic Tissues via Embedded Volumetric Printing of**
1039 **Microgels**

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1046 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES**

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1049 **Supplementary Figure S1:** Granular constructs characterised by irregular microparticles. i) Optical
1050 microscopy image of a volumetric printed constructs, stained with Trypan blue to facilitate
1051 visualization, showing the particulate composition. ii) Light-sheet imaging of the irregularly-shaped
1052 microparticles.

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1055 **Supplementary Figure S2:** Effect of the microstructure of the microgel based gels on hMSC cells
 1056 differentiation into adipocytes. Quantification of the number of adipocytes per field view in bulk and
 1057 gelMA μResin, cultured with and without insulin in the differentiation medium.

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1060 **Supplementary Figure S3:** Representative (n=3) photorheologies of GG/PEGDA ink and μResin.

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1064 **Supplementary Figure S4:** Effect of the extruded features on the volumetric printing process and on
 1065 the resolution of the final construct. Printing accuracy (n=5), calculated on the bigger (D) and smaller
 1066 (d) diameters of the galaxy-shape model, and dimensions comparison of the galaxy-tips, as a function
 1067 of the different volumes of i β -cells-laded bioink extruded in the middle: i = 1 μL ; ii = 5 μL ; iii = 10
 1068 μL . i β -cells concentration: 30×10^6 cells/mL. Scale bars: overviews = 1 mm; magnifications = 0.1 mm.

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1073 **Supplementary Figure S5:** Complex multicellular 3D construct representing a pancreas model
1074 were produced by mixing the red-labelled stromal compartment (MSC, Vybrant DiD membrane
1075 staining), and via extrusion printing of clusters of green-labelled pancreatic cells (β -cells, Vybrant
1076 DiO). Tomographic light projections were applied to volumetrically print the outer pancreas shape
1077 and the inner channels representing the main branches of the vasculature. A) and B) show two
1078 randomly selected confocal scanning fluorescence microscopy cross sections with an open printed
1079 channel visible in B). Scale bars: A = 500 μ m; B = 1 mm.

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1082 **Supplementary Figure S6:** Viability quantification on Live/Dead images at day 1 and day 7 (n=3)
1083 of iβ-cells bioprinted with different approaches: volumetric bioprinted in bulk gelMA (Bulk VP) at a
1084 cell density of 2.5 million cells/mL. Volumetric bioprinted in μResin (μResin VP) at a cell density of
1085 2.5 million cells/mL. Casted μResin (μResin Cast) at a cell density of 2.5 million cells/mL. Extruded
1086 at a cell density of 30 million cells/mL (EmP - extr) in a 2.5 million cells/mL-laden and casted μResin
1087 (EmP - cast). Extruded at a cell density of 30 million cells/mL (EmVP - extr) in a 2.5 million cells/mL-
1088 laden and volumetric printed μResin (EmVP - VP). The latter condition represent the EmVP process
1089 described in the manuscript.

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1092 **Supplementary Figure S7:** NanoLuc levels in cell culture supernatants (n=3) of the extruded and
1093 mixed iβ-cells quantified using the Nano-Glo Luciferase Assay System (N1110, Promega) (cc =
1094 50x10⁶ iβ-cells /mL not extruded).